

北京科学技术情报学会

Beijing Science & Technology Information Society(BSTIS)

2023年3月30日 北京科学技术情报学会 第十届
理事会审议通过 成立 元科学专业委员会

元科学专业委员会

Metasciences Committee

开放 · 透明 · 共享 · 包容
Open, Transparent, Sharing and Inclusive

李杰 副研究员

中国科学院 文献情报中心

创建“元科学专业委员会”的思考

- 当前，数据驱动与人工智能交融发展，人类生产生活以及学习正在发生深刻的变化。在数智驱动的背景下，科学研究的范式在悄然变化。在新的变化下，凝聚新的科学共同体力量，聚焦新兴的研究问题意义重大。当前，国外已经有相关机构关注并研究元科学，国内很少有学者关注，且尚无协会组织建立“元科学专业委员会”。
- 元科学专业委员会（**Metasciences committee**）就是在此背景下创建成立的新兴跨学科的专业委员会。其构建的基础思路形成以科学学与科学计量学为主要成员，联合科学学、科技哲学、科学史学的学者，共同采用定性与定量的方法，为复杂科学问题的解决提供方案。
“以定性定量的科学方法来认识科学，并力求为复杂信息环境下决策提供方案”。
- 活动形式：1) 学术讲座；2) 教育培训；3) 学术会议等。

science → ecneics

科学家如何认识自己？科学家如何认识科学？科学家如何面对信任危机？科学研究如何更好地服务政策的制定？

Ioannidis, J., Boyack, K., Small, H. et al. Bibliometrics: Is your most cited work your best?. *Nature* 514, 561–562 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1038/514561a>

Metascience的内涵

- **Metascience** is the use of scientific methodology to study science itself (科学学与科学计量学). Metascience seeks to increase the quality of scientific research while reducing inefficiency (科技创新政策学). It is also known as “research on research (Meta research)” and “the science of science (科学学)”, as it uses research methods to study how research is done and find where **improvements** can be made.
- Metascience concerns itself with all fields of research and has been described as “a **bird’s eye view of science** (科学结构图)”. In the words of John Ioannidis, “Science is the best thing that has happened to human beings... but we can do it better.” (来自维基百科).

Toward to the Science sustainability

You never change things by fighting the existing reality. To change something, build a new model that makes the existing model obsolete. – Buckminster Fuller

元科学 Metasciences

定性定量与跨学科方案融合
Solutions Fusion

数据(Data)
算法(Algorithm)
场景(scenario)

坚持问题导向
做负责的科研
构建优良的科研生态与文化

数据与情报专家
Data and information Expert

量化科学研究
数据与算法驱动
Quantitative Science Studies
Scientometrics / informetrics / Bibliometrics

科学、技术、创新政策分析
STI & Policy
学科领域、政策以及智库专家
Domain Expert

负责任
Responsible

开放
Open

元科学群
Metasciences

透明
Transparent

共享
Sharing

诚信
Research Integrity

包容
Inclusive

创新
Innovation

元科学专业委员会“一体两翼”：
以科学学与科技哲学为主体理论
指导，以量化科学模型、算法和
科学技术政策创新分析为两翼，
实现定性定量与跨学科方案融合，
以解决复杂科学问题。

Science of Science

以科学学与科技哲学为理论基座

BSTIS委员会

• 工作委员会:

1. 学术工作委员会
2. 普及教育工作委员会
3. 青年工作委员会
4. 改革与创新工作委员会

• 专业委员会:

1. 信息技术专业委员会
2. 信息资源专业委员会
3. 信息研究与信息咨询专业委员会
4. 知识管理与竞争情报专业委员会
5. 信息安全专业委员会
6. 高等院校科技情报专业委员会
7. 企业信息专业委员会

元科学专业委员会(筹)

定性定量与跨学科方案融合
Solutions Fusion

支撑
←

数据(Data)
算法(Algorithm)
场景(scenario)

坚持问题导向
做负责的科研
构建优良的科研生态与文化

信息专家
Information Expert
↓

量化科学研究
数据与算法驱动
Scientometrics / Informetrics / Bibliometrics
Quantitative Science Studies

科学、技术、STI & Policy
学科领域、政策以及智库专家
Domain Expert
↓
创新政策分析

Science of Science

以科学学与科技哲学为理论基座

元科学专业委员会 的关联委员会

目前，国内尚无“元科学专业委员会”，过去5年，国外已经成立了相关组织和机构，已经有成系列的学术会议。

1. 中国科学学与科技政策学研究会 科学计量学与信息计量学专业委员会
2. 中国科学学与科技政策学会 科学学理论与学科建设专业委员会
3. 国际科学计量与信息计量学会（ISSI）

与元科学相关的研究在蓬勃发展

1. 医学、心理学领域的可重复危机，促进了Meta-analysis的兴起以及负责人的科学研究的讨论。
2. 科研大数据的到来，人工智能、复杂网络等蓬勃发展，数据驱动型的科学发现收到热切的关注。数据+智能+专家 的科学范式已经形成并取得了瞩目的成就。
3. 新的时代背景下，“范式”一词又变得流行。促使科学界对科学学，科技哲学的再认识。元科学群的春天已经到来！学者们开始反思科学本身....

.....

Science of Science 元科学的时代背景—— 科研大数据时代与数据驱动的科学学新发展

THE SCIENCE OF SCIENCE

Dashun Wang
Albert-László Barabási

RESEARCH

Corrected 9 July 2018. See full text.

REVIEW

SCIENCE COMMUNITY

Science of science

Santo Fortunato,^{1,2*} Carl T. Bergstrom,³ Katy Börner,^{2,4} James A. Evans,⁵ Dirk Helbing,⁶ Staša Milojević,¹ Alexander M. Petersen,⁷ Filippo Radicchi,¹ Roberta Sinatra,^{8,9} Brian Uzzi,^{10,11,12} Alessandro Vespignani,^{10,13,14} Ludo Waltman,¹⁵ Dashun Wang,^{13,15} Albert-László Barabási^{1,2,16,17,18}

Identifying fundamental drivers of science and developing predictive models to capture its evolution are instrumental for the design of policies that can improve the scientific enterprise—for example, through enhanced career paths for scientists, better performance evaluation for organizations hosting research, discovery of novel effective funding vehicles, and even identification of promising regions along the scientific frontier. The science of science uses large-scale data on the production of science to search for universal and domain-specific patterns. Here, we review recent developments in this transdisciplinary field.

The deluge of digital data on scholarly output offers unprecedented opportunities to explore patterns characterizing the structure and evolution of science. The science of science (SciSci) places the practice of science itself under the microscope, leading to a quantitative understanding of the genesis of scientific discovery, creativity, and practice and developing tools and policies aimed at accelerating scientific progress.

The emergence of SciSci has been driven by two key factors. The first is data availability. In addition to the proprietary Web of Science (WoS), the historic first citation index (J), multiple data sources are available today (Scopus, PubMed, Google Scholar, Microsoft Academic, the U.S. Patent and Trademark Office, and others). Some of these sources are freely accessible, covering

millions of data points pertaining to scientists and their output and capturing research from all over the world and all branches of science. Second, SciSci has benefited from an influx of and collaborations among natural, computational, and social scientists who have developed big data-based capabilities and enabled critical tests of generative models that aim to capture the unfolding of science, its institutions, and its workforce.

One distinctive characteristic of this emerging field is how it breaks down disciplinary boundaries. SciSci integrates findings and theories from multiple disciplines and uses a wide range of data and methods. From scientometrics, it takes the idea of measuring science from large-scale data sources; from the sociology of sciences, it adopts theoretical concepts and social processes;

and from innovation studies, it explores and identifies pathways through which science contributes to innovation and economic change. SciSci relies on a broad collection of quantitative methods, from descriptive statistics and data visualization to advanced econometric methods, network science approaches, machine-learning algorithms, mathematical analysis, and computer simulation, including agent-based modeling. The value proposition of SciSci hinges on the hypothesis that with a deeper understanding of the factors behind successful science, we can enhance the prospects of science as a whole to more effectively address societal problems.

Networks of scientists, institutions, and ideas

Contemporary science is a dynamical system of undertakings driven by complex interactions among social structures, knowledge representations, and the natural world. Scientific knowledge is constituted by concepts and relations embodied in research papers, books, patents, software, and other scholarly artifacts, organized into scientific disciplines and broader fields. These social, conceptual, and material elements are connected through formal and informal flows of information, ideas, research practices, tools, and samples. Science can thus be described as a complex, self-organizing, and constantly evolving multiagent network.

Early studies discovered an exponential growth in the volume of scientific literature (2), a trend that continues with an average doubling period of 15 years (Fig. 1). Yet, it would be naive to equate the growth of the scientific literature with the growth of scientific ideas. Changes in the publishing world, both technological and economic, have led to increasing efficiency in the production of publications. Moreover, new publications in science tend to cluster in discrete areas of knowledge (3). Large-scale text analysis,

Fig. 1. Growth of science. (A) Annual production of scientific articles indexed in the WoS database. (B) Growth of ideas covered by articles indexed in the WoS. This was determined by counting unique title phrases in a fixed number of articles (4).

¹Center for Complex Networks and Systems Research, School of Informatics, Computing, and Engineering, Indiana University, Bloomington, IN 47408, USA; ²Indiana University Network Science Institute, Indiana University, Bloomington, IN 47408, USA; ³Department of Biology, University of Washington, Seattle, WA 98195-8300, USA; ⁴Cyberinfrastructure for Network Science Center, School of Informatics, Computing, and Engineering, Indiana University, Bloomington, IN 47408, USA; ⁵Department of Sociology, University of Chicago, Chicago, IL 60637, USA; ⁶Computational Social Science, ETH Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland; ⁷Ernest and Julio Gallo Management Program, School of Engineering, University of California, Merced, CA 95343, USA; ⁸Center for Network Science, Central European University, Budapest 1052, Hungary; ⁹Department of Mathematics, Central European University, Budapest 1024, Hungary; ¹⁰Institute for Network Science, Northeastern University, Boston, MA 02115, USA; ¹¹College of Management, Northeastern University, Evanston, IL 60208, USA; ¹²Northeastern Institute on Complex Systems, Northeastern University, Evanston, IL 60208, USA; ¹³Laboratory for the Modeling of Biological and Sociochemical Systems, Northeastern University, Boston, MA 02115, USA; ¹⁴ISI Foundation, Turin 10123, Italy; ¹⁵Centre for Science and Technology Studies, Leiden University, Leiden, Netherlands; ¹⁶Center for Cancer Systems Biology, Dana-Farber Cancer Institute, Boston, MA 02115, USA; ¹⁷Corresponding author. Email: santo@indiana.edu (S.F.); barabasi@gmail.com (A.-L.B.)

Corrected 9 July 2018. See full text.

RESEARCH

REVIEW SUMMARY

SCIENCE COMMUNITY

Science of science

Santo Fortunato,^{*} Carl T. Bergstrom, Katy Börner, James A. Evans, Dirk Helbing, Staša Milojević, Alexander M. Petersen, Filippo Radicchi, Roberta Sinatra, Brian Uzzi, Alessandro Vespignani, Ludo Waltman, Dashun Wang, Albert-László Barabási^{*}

BACKGROUND: The increasing availability of digital data on scholarly inputs and outputs—from research funding, productivity, and collaboration to paper citations and scientist mobility—offers unprecedented opportunities to explore the structure and evolution of science. The science of science (SciSci) offers a quantitative understanding of the interactions among scientific agents across diverse geographic and temporal scales. It provides insights into the conditions underlying creativity and the genesis of scientific discovery, with the ultimate goal of developing tools and policies that have the potential to accelerate science. In the past decade, SciSci has benefited from an influx of natural, computational, and social scientists who together have developed big data-based capabilities for empirical analysis and generative modeling that capture the unfolding of science, its institutions, and its workforce. The value proposition of SciSci is that with a deeper understanding of the factors that drive successful science, we can more effectively address environmental, societal, and technological problems.

ADVANCES: Science can be described as a complex, self-organizing, and evolving network of scholars, projects, papers, and ideas. This representation has unveiled patterns characterizing the emergence of new scientific fields through the study of collaboration networks and the path of impactful discoveries through the study of citation networks. Microscopic models have traced the dynamics of citation accumulation, allowing us to predict the future impact of individual papers. SciSci has revealed choices and trade-offs that scientists face as they advance both their own careers and the scientific horizon. For example, measurements indicate that scholars are risk-averse, preferring to study topics related to their current expertise, which constrains the potential of future discoveries. Those willing to break this pattern engage in riskier careers but become more likely to make major breakthroughs. Overall, the highest-impact science is grounded in conventional combinations of prior work but features unusual combinations. Last, as the locus of research is shifting into teams, SciSci is increasingly focused on

the impact of team research, finding that small teams tend to disrupt science and technology with new ideas drawing on older and less prevalent ones. In contrast, large teams tend to develop recent, popular ideas, obtaining high, but often short-lived, impact.

OUTLOOK: SciSci offers a deep quantitative understanding of the relational structure between scientists, institutions, and ideas because it facilitates the identification of fundamental mechanisms responsible for scientific discovery. These interdisciplinary data-driven efforts complement contributions from related fields such as scientometrics and the economics and sociology of science. Although SciSci seeks long-standing universal laws and mechanisms that apply across various fields of science, a fundamental challenge going forward is accounting for

undeniable differences in culture, habits, and preferences between different fields and countries. This variation makes some cross-domain insights difficult to appreciate and associated sciences policies difficult to implement. The differences among the questions, data, and skills specific to each discipline suggest that further insights can be gained from domain-specific SciSci studies, which model and identify opportunities adapted to the needs of individual research fields. ■

The list of author affiliations is available in the full article online. ^{*}Corresponding author. Email: santo@indiana.edu (S.F.); barabasi@gmail.com (A.-L.B.)
Cite this article as: Fortunato et al., *Science* 359, eaao0185 (2018). DOI: 10.1126/science.aao0185

Research on research

A growing number of scientists is studying science itself.

ENSERINK M. Research on research [J]. Science, 2018, 361(6408): 1178-9.

<https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.361.6408.1178>

WORLD VIEW A personal take on events

Metascience could rescue the 'replication crisis'

Independent replication of studies before publication may reveal sources of unreliable results, says Jonathan W. Schooler.

元科学可以拯救“可重复危机”

If you witness a bank robbery, what did you see? And then, in a line-up? That sounds like the right response, but it might not be. Almost 25 years ago, a colleague and I published a psychology study (J. W. Schooler and T. Y. Engstler-Schooler *Cogn. Psychol.* 22, 36-71; 1990) that indicated that to describe the physical appearance of the criminal could make it harder for a witness to subsequently identify the person they saw.

The effect is called 'verbal overshadowing' and its discovery proved controversial, and not simply because of what it means for detectives. Over the years, other researchers (myself included) have had mixed success replicating the finding. Some have doubted whether it exists at all. That 1990 research project has been used as an example of the 'replication crisis' that has engulfed science in recent years. In disciplines such as medicine, psychology, genetics and biology, researchers have been confronted with results that are not as robust as they originally seemed.

In response, scientists have launched various replication projects to assess the robustness of published research. In psychology, numerous labs have volunteered to re-run studies, with the methods vetted by the original researchers. My discovery of the verbal-overshadowing effect was an obvious target for this approach, and so, last year, psychologists at 31 different laboratories across the world signed up to repeat the study and report the results.

How did I feel about having work scrutinized in this way? I thought that I could not lose. Positive replication would confirm the important verbal-overshadowing effect. Failure to replicate would be more evidence for the 'decline effect', an idea I endorse that the size of an effect decreases over repeated replications, for reasons that are not fully understood.

Unfortunately for a replication study, there was a mistake in the timing parameters of the initial experimental protocol. Still, this unexpected negative turn of events took a positive spin as the deviation from the original protocol, once identified and fixed, generated some useful comparative data.

Some 22 of the original 31 repeating labs went on to follow the corrected study protocol. Pooled, the results confirmed the original finding. The verbal-overshadowing effect was clearly demonstrated (although the effect size was smaller than in our 1990 research and observed only when the original parameters, in the corrected protocol, were followed).

The outcome is a genuine victory for the emerging field of metascience, an approach in which science turns the lens of scrutiny on itself. Metascience, the science of science, uses rigorous methods to examine how scientific practices

distinguished from the former by a reliance on quantitative analysis, and from the latter by a broad focus on the general factors that contribute to the limitations and successes of research.

Large-scale replication efforts such as this one are important, but they are expensive, time-consuming and impracticable for the vast majority of scientific studies. Rather than focus exclusively on whether past studies stand up, we need a clearer sense of the processes that influence the reliability of new findings. These could include how 'invested' researchers are in the original hypothesis, the number of times a protocol is repeated and how the methods and outcomes are assessed and written up.

WE NEED A CLEARER SENSE OF THE PROCESSES THAT INFLUENCE THE RELIABILITY OF NEW FINDINGS.

Together with labs at three other universities, my research group has begun an initiative to test the reproducibility of our science. Rather than re-examine published studies, each lab has agreed to allow the other three to generate new findings, replicate each others' experiments and compare the results of new studies before they are published. We will then be able to judge differences, for example, in the results obtained by the originating lab compared with those that follow the idea, and so, in theory, have less invested in the results.

It is clearly not feasible for all researchers to follow this approach in their routine work. But it should offer a valuable academic exercise to examine the factors that affect reproducibility as they arise during the course of research.

By pre-registering all aspects of new scientific studies and then repeatedly trying to replicate them, the project allows careful scrutiny of all parts of the research process, from inception to replication. If the studies replicate flawlessly, we will have established a gold standard for reproducible studies. If they do not, then our approach will present an opportunity to rigorously assess the reasons.

Some might suggest that the focus on replication within psychology is an indictment of the field. It is precisely the opposite. All fields face problems with reproducibility, and psychology should be applauded for its willingness to tackle the issue empirically.

In fact, psychological science has long been at the forefront of refining and improving the scientific process. The understanding of experimenter expectancy effects (a form of cognitive bias) and the importance of double-blind trials emerged first in psychology. Such self-examination can only strengthen the scientific process for all. ■

➔ **NATURE.COM**
Discuss this article
online at:
[go.nature.com/8iabws](https://www.nature.com/8iabws)

Jonathan W. Schooler is a psychologist at the University of California, Santa Barbara.
e-mail: jonathanwschooler@gmail.com

Schooler, J. Metascience could rescue the 'replication crisis'.
Nature 515, 9 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1038/515009a>

元科学的时代背景——科研大数据时代与数据驱动的科学学新发展

- Fortunato, S., Bergstrom, C. T., Börner, K., Evans, J. A., Helbing, D., Milojević, S., Petersen, A. M., Radicchi, F., Sinatra, R., Uzzi, B., Vespignani, A., Waltman, L., Wang, D., & Barabási, A.-L. (2018). Science of science. *Science*, 359(6379), eaao0185. 科学的科学。
- Gomez, C.J., Herman, A.C. & Parigi, P. Leading countries in global science increasingly receive more citations than other countries doing similar research. *Nat Hum Behav* 6, 919–929 (2022). 引文网络分析揭示全球科研不平等加剧：混圈子正阻止新想法诞生
- Li, W., Aste, T., Caccioli, F. et al. Reciprocity and impact in academic careers. *EPJ Data Sci.* 8, 20 (2019). 46万条引文数据揭示互惠引用的潜在危害
- Wuchty, S., Jones, B. F., & Uzzi, B. (2007). The increasing dominance of teams in production of knowledge. *Science*, 316(5827), 1036-1039.
- Sinatra, R.; Wang, D.; Deville, P.; Song, C.; Barabasi, A.-L. (2016). Quantifying the evolution of individual scientific impact. *Science*, 354(6312), 量化个体科学影响的演变
- Wu, L., Wang, D. & Evans, J.A. Large teams develop and small teams disrupt science and technology. *Nature* 566, 378–382 (2019). 大团队稳步发展，小团队突破式创新。
- Zeng, A., Fan, Y., Di, Z. et al. Fresh teams are associated with original and multidisciplinary research. *Nat Hum Behav* 5, 1314–1322 (2021). 海量论文数据解释了新团队在原创性研究和跨学科影响力上的关键作用
- Park, M., Leahey, E. & Funk, R.J. Papers and patents are becoming less disruptive over time. *Nature* 613, 138–144 (2023). 论文和专利的创新程度越来越低。
- Miao, L., Murray, D., Jung, WS. et al. The latent structure of global scientific development. *Nat Hum Behav* 6, 1206–1217 (2022). 3700万篇论文构建学科网络，揭示全球科学产出的隐藏结构
- Nielsen, M. W., & Andersen, J. P. (2021). Global citation inequality is on the rise. *proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 118(7), e2012208118. 2600万篇论文引用调查：科研界马太效应加剧，强强联合愈发普遍

Metascience期刊

Volume 6

[September 1997, issue 2](#)

[January 1997, issue 1](#)

Volume 5

[September 1996, issue 2](#)

[March 1996, issue 1](#)

创刊于1996年以前。

Aims and scope

Metascience is a review journal which publishes high quality, comprehensive reviews of books in the fields of **history and philosophy of science and science and technology studies**.

Metascience is non-specialist in that reviews are accessible to a wide cross-section of the science studies community.

- Presents high quality reviews of books in the fields of **history and philosophy of science, and science and technology studies**.
- Includes such innovations as essay reviews, non-anglophone reviews, discipline survey reviews and 'round-tables' in which up to four reviewers provide independent essay reviews of one book.
- The contents are accessible to a **wide cross-section of the science studies community**.

Editors:

K. Brad Wray, Aarhus University, Denmark
Jonathan Simon, Université de Lorraine, France

Managing Editor:

Lori Nash, Aarhus University, Denmark

Editorial Board:

Theodore Arabatzis, University of Athens, Greece

Luciano Boschiero, Campion College, Australia

George Gale, UMKC, Kansas City, USA

Michel Ghins, Université Catholique de Louvain, Belgium

Michael D. Gordin, Princeton University, USA

Robin Hendry, University of Durham, UK

Alan C. Love, University of Minnesota, USA

Michael E. Lynch, Cornell University, Ithaca, USA

Louella McCarthy, University of Wollongong, Australia

Richard Menary, Macquarie University, Australia

David Mercer, University of Wollongong, Australia

Australia

David P. Miller, University of New South Wales, Australia

Stathis Psillos, University of Athens, Greece

Laura Ruetsche, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, USA

He has published papers in the following areas: (i) the social epistemology of science, (ii) **Kuhn's philosophy of science**, (iii) the anti-realism/realism debate in **philosophy of science**, and (iv) collective intentionality. Please do not hesitate to contact me if you are interested in one of my papers.

I have published three books with Cambridge University Press, **Kuhn's Evolutionary Social Epistemology** (2011), **Resisting Scientific Realism** (2018), and **Kuhn's Intellectual Path: Charting The Structure of Scientific Revolutions** (2021). I have recently edited a collection of articles, **Interpreting Kuhn: Critical Essays** (also with CUP; 2021).

<https://www.springer.com/journal/11016>

Metascience会议

A global gathering for knowledge sharing, community building, and opportunities to define a roadmap of research and intervention priorities to accelerate science.

Details Speakers Partners and Sponsors Prior Conferences COS Merchandise Register

METASCIENCE

2023 CONFERENCE

A global gathering for knowledge sharing, community building, and opportunities to define a roadmap of research and intervention priorities to accelerate science.

May 9-10, 2023

In-person conference at the National Academy of Sciences
Washington, DC

REGISTER NOW \$85 for students, \$150 for non-students

<https://metascience.info/>

Metascience 2023 is supported by the Center for Open Science and Astera Institute. 由开放科学中心和Astera研究所支持。会议地点：美国科学院

"The Metascience Conference was an entirely invigorating experience. I got to meet and hear from metaresearchers I have long followed. It inspired me to pursue ideas and methodologies I would have not considered otherwise."

Jason Chin
Senior Lecturer, Australian National University

Pierre
Azoulay
MIT Sloan School of Management
National Bureau of Economic Research

Abel
Brodeur
University of Ottawa

Katie
Corker
Grand Valley State University

Sarah
de Rijcke
Leiden University
Research on Research Institute (RoRI)

Ulrich
Dirnagl
Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin
Berlin Institute of Health

Tim
Errington
Center for Open Science

Chelle
Gentemann
NASA Transform to Open Science
Mission

Jordi
Goodman
Boston University School of Law
MIT

Metascience会议

Networks in Science of Science

Mario Krenn
@MarioKrenn6240

Interested in using Network Science for analysing Millions of Research papers? #MetaScience

Join the #NetSci2023 conference in Vienna (10-14 July 2023) & "Networks in Science of Science" workshop: netscisci.github.io

Organized by Harlin Lee @RishiSonthalia @phil_of_ai

翻译推文

netscisci.github.io
Overview
A NetSci 2023 Satellite Workshop

下午5:38 · 2023年2月25日 · 14 查看

Interested in using Network Science for analysing Millions of Research papers? #MetaScience

Background

The vast amount of research articles, preprints, grant proposals, and patents produced by scientists provide a rich digital trace of the scientific ecosystem. This data is the foundation of an emerging field called the "**Science of Science**", which aims to understand the evolution of science in a quantitative manner. This field has the potential to bring significant benefits in terms of scientific, technological, and educational advancement. Networks are a useful and intuitive tool for understanding the connections between various elements in the scientific community, such as scientists, institutions, journals, conferences, ideas, theories, and funding agencies.

This satellite workshop invites researchers and practitioners to share their latest findings and developments in the area of **network science applied to the study of science**. This is a particularly exciting time to discuss new studies on rich representations (such as hypergraphs) or new deep-learning-based methods of predicting and understanding. We aim to bring together an **interdisciplinary** group of researchers to reflect the diverse community that can drive (and benefit from) scientific innovation. In addition, this workshop presents an excellent opportunity for more **junior researchers** (such as graduate students, postdocs, and pre-tenure professors) to gain exposure within the field. This will serve as a platform for them to present ongoing research, receive feedback and guidance from more experienced researchers, and network with potential mentors, collaborators, and funders.

This is a continuation of previous successful workshops and conferences on organized by **members of our PC** on Science of Science, both from within and outside NetSci: "International Conference on the Science of Science and Innovation" (2022), "Science of Team Science & Innovation" (NetSci 2022), "Knowledge Networks in Science and Technology" (NetSci 2017), the "Annual International Conference on Computational Social Science" (2015-2022), "International Symposium on the Science of Science" (2016), "Quantifying Science" (Conference on Complex Systems 2015). The success of these workshops is attributed to the continued interest and engagement from the network science community in the study of the Science of Science.

Metascience组织机构: METASCIENCE RESEARCH LAB (MSRL)

与本委员会的使命和关注最为相近。

Search

[ABOUT US](#) [PUBLICATIONS](#) [PROJECTS](#) [MEMBERS](#) [NEWS](#) [RESOURCES](#)

METASCIENCE RESEARCH LAB (MSRL)

ABOUT US

We are the Metascience Research Lab (MSRL) at the [Information School](#) of [University of Wisconsin-Madison](#)! Founded in 2020 by Drs. [B. Ian Hutchins](#) and [Chaoqun Ni](#), MSRL is the nexus for research on the Science of Science, Science Policy, and Scientometrics at iSchool. We study complex data to identify insights for accelerating research advances, cultivating a competitive scientific workforce, and facilitating scientific knowledge transfer. Our goal is to provide evidence to inform policies and practices on effective scientific resource allocation, strategy development, and infrastructure building.

ALERT: We are always looking for highly motivated students to join us!

OUR RESEARCH

DATA-DRIVEN SCIENCE POLICY

- * Data-driven insights for science funders
- * Evidence-based science and technology policy

KNOWLEDGE DISCOVERY

- * Research frontier prediction
- * Knowledge extraction

INEQUALITY IN SCIENCE

- * Gender and race disparities in science
- * Diversity, equity and inclusion in science workforce

SCIENTOMETRICS

- * Evaluative metrics for science
- * Open science

Ian Hutchins

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7657-552X>

Ian Hutchins is an Assistant Professor of Data and Information Science at the University of Wisconsin-Madison Information School. Prof. Hutchins previously worked as a data scientist at NIH, where he developed the [iCite](#) bibliometrics dashboard, along with many of its quantitative metrics and the [NIH Open Citation Collection](#) database. He also coached high school fencing for nearly a decade.

Chaoqun Ni · UW-Madison iSchool

Welcome! I am an Assistant Professor at the [Information School](#), University of Wisconsin-Madison. I am also an affiliated faculty member of the [Holtz Center for Science & Technology Studies](#), and [Center for Demography of Health and Aging \(CDHA\)](#). Prior to this, I was an Assistant Professor at the University of Iowa and Simmons University. I study science, scholarship, and the scientific workforce using massive data to inform decision-making in science policy and to better understand the doing of science. I teach in the areas of information technology, database management, statistical data analysis, data interoperability, information visualization, and research methods. I got my Ph.D. in Information Science (minor in Statistics) from the School of Informatics and Computing, Indiana University Bloomington.

I am looking for **highly-motivated Ph.D. students** to work on cutting-edge problems in the science of science, scientific workforce diversity, scholarly data mining & analytics, and science policy. Students with interests and background in NLP, statistics, sociology, and information science are welcome to apply. Please contact me **by email** if you are interested.

I am a member of the [Metascience Research Lab](#) at UW-Madison!

Metascience 组织机构 Research of Research

We want to improve how research is funded, practiced, communicated, and evaluated, so that it works better for everybody.

<https://researchonresearch.org/>

James Wilsdon

Director, RoRI
Professor of Research Policy
University College London
ORCID iD 0000-0002-5395-5949
Twitter @jameswilsdon

An interdisciplinary social scientist, James Wilsdon works on the politics and governance of research. Over his career, in addition to academic posts at the universities of Sheffield, Sussex and Lancaster, he has worked in think tanks and as director of science policy for the Royal Society, the UK's national academy of science.

Gert Vilhelm Balling

Co-Chair, RoRI
PhD, Senior Impact Partner at the Impact
Department at the Novo Nordisk
Foundation (NNF), Denmark.
ORCID iD 0000-0001-9918-8610

Gert is a Senior Impact Partner at NNF where he has worked since 2014. He is co-responsible for the implementation and continuous development of impact assessment in the Foundation as well as presentation of impact results to internal and external stakeholders.

Sarah de Rijcke

Co-Chair, RoRI
Professor of Science and Evaluation Studies and
Director, CWTS
ORCID iD 0000-0003-4652-0362
Twitter @sarahderijcke

Sarah is Professor of Science and Evaluation Studies and Director of the Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS) at Leiden University. Sarah also leads the Science and Evaluation Studies research group at CWTS. Her research interests include academic valuation and evaluation processes, changing research cultures, knowledge infrastructures, and roles of research in and for society.

Ludo Waltman

Associate Director, RoRI
Professor of Quantitative Science Studies and
Deputy Director, CWTS
ORCID iD 0000-0001-8249-1752
Twitter @LudoWaltman

Ludo is Professor of Quantitative Science Studies and deputy director at the Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS) at Leiden University. Ludo's research group focuses on the use of scientometric methods to address problems in research management and science policy.

Juergen Wastl

Associate Director, RoRI
Director of Academic Relations and Consultancy,
Digital Science
ORCID iD 0000-0001-7757-8001
Twitter @juergen_wastl

Juergen leads the Digital Science consultancy portfolio, supporting research institutions, funders, governments and other institutions with research capabilities to make better use of data to inform their strategies and decisions. A Molecular Biologist & Biochemist by training, Juergen has held roles in project management and research strategy in Industry and Higher Education.

Helen Buckley Woods

Postdoctoral Research Associate, RoRI
Information School, University of Sheffield
ORCID iD 0000-0002-0653-9803
Twitter @HelenBWoods

Helen is a social scientist with a background in library and information science, and has a doctorate in higher education studies focusing on the increased demands for instrumental research and knowledge dissemination in UK universities. Her experience at Sheffield's School of Health and Related Research has focused on information retrieval and evidence synthesis.

METASCIENCE

THE SCIENCE OF DOING SCIENCE

请各位专家学者指正！